

Chasing Ghosts on the Airbnb Platform

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Summary

The rise of Airbnb has come with considerable costs to cities, not least the growth of a shadow industry of seemingly individualised homes that are, in fact, part of a large portfolio and some of which evade regulations intended to protect long-term lettings. However, since these listings are *designed* to appear distinct, *detecting* the scale of these operations presents significant challenges. This paper presents early work intended to examine how Natural Language Processing techniques can augment existing spatial analytic ones in order to assist in the detection of ghosts.

KEYWORDS: Natural Language Processing, Machine Learning, Airbnb, New York, London

1. Introduction

Although the rise of the ‘sharing’ economy has yielded benefits to the *users* of short-term letting platforms such as Airbnb, this has come at considerable costs to cities and their residents (Wachsmuth and Weisler A 2018). From Boston (Horn and Merante 2017) to Barcelona (Garcia-López *et al.* 2020), cities with tight housing markets have been heavily impacted as landlords shift properties into the more immediately profitable Short-Term Lettings (STL) market.

2. Ghost in the Shell

This has led to the emergence of a shadow industry that masks the ‘status’ of properties. Some are legitimate businesses that have ‘professionalised’ the sector by, for instance, managing listings on behalf of individual owners (*e.g.* [guestready.com](#), [cityrelay.com](#), and [smarthost.co.uk](#)). Others operate illegally, though this can vary from the scale of an individual circumventing length-of-listing rules for a single property (Airbnb nd) up to an organisation operating a virtual property empire (Ferré-Sadurní 2019). This work is primarily concerned with the latter groups, termed ‘ghosts’ by many (*e.g.* Wieditz 2017, Porter 2019), since their operation not only deprives cities of an understanding of the scale of STL market activity, it also deprives many cities of income from taxation and may put people at risk since required safety infrastructure and inspections may also be omitted.

1.1. Towards a Typology of Ghosts

There are two challenging aspects to approaching this work from a quantitative standpoint: the first is that there may well be several different types of ghosts at work within Airbnb and other STL aggregators and relatively little formal work has been done about how professionalization may be impacting use of the platforms; the second is that, as intended by the term ‘ghost’, there is a sense of hidden activity whose presence is only indirectly visible to those seeking to research this issue. Based on a typology of visible users, we believe that there may be four (or more) distinct types of ‘ghost’ at work on the Airbnb platform:

1. *Ghost Hotels* where multiple apartments/flats in a single building are listed separately.
2. *Ghost Hostels* where multiple rooms in an apartment/flat are listed separately.
3. *Ghost Operators* where multiple listings across the city are linked in non-obvious ways.

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4. *Ghost Properties* where a single property is listed multiple times.

In each case, the defining feature of these ghosts is that the operational management of the property/properties is concealed from end-users and, potentially, regulators. Implicitly, the challenge of tackling this problem quantitatively is that the ghost listings are *designed* to avoid detection and, consequently, *finding* them presents something of a challenge.

Traditional spatial analytical techniques *alone* are insufficient since proximity in space alone is not a defining feature of all ghost-types. Consequently, this paper presents early work intended to examine how Natural Language Processing and related textual analytic techniques can augment spatial analytic approaches to assist in the detection of ghosts.

1.2. Ghostbusting

Using data from InsideAirbnb, we hope to see evidence that text-analytical approaches can be used to reveal some aspects of this shadow sector's operations on the Airbnb platform. In our initial work we focus on the market in New York City though, in principle, the same code could be applied to any *Anglophone* city with minimal alteration. Although InsideAirbnb provides some historical data free of charge, with older data available upon application, our focus here is on the data from 2021.

Drawing on the typology set out above, we then employ three criteria in our search for ghosts: spatial, textual, temporal[†] and amenity-based similarity. In all cases we assume that, as distance between any pair of listings across one or more of these dimensions decreases, the likelihood of there being a connection between them—whether explicit or not—increases. We are then able to use the more visible mirror-listings to validate our approach: for instance, the process for tracking Ghost Hotels should also, quite naturally, pick up real hotels as well.

3. Methods

While spatial proximity is not a useful predictor for Ghost Operators (those who manage multiple properties across a city), and taking into account Airbnb's shuffling process, the maximum distance between a pair of listings at the same address should be no more than 300 metres. This provides a threshold for classification purposes: only properties within this distance are candidate ghost hotels, hostels, or properties.

Amenity proximity is drawn from a list of searchable attributes: similar to a keyword search, Airbnb prompts users to choose from standardised list but users are also free to create their own. We hypothesise that anyone fitting out multiple properties (or listing the same property multiple times) will default to providing a similar set of amenities and, consequently, that a low Minimum Edit Distance between pairs of listings will be a good indicator of 'relatedness'.

Finally, to measure textual similarity our initial focus is on the use of document-level proximity using Word2Vec and Doc2Vec (Mikolov *et al.* 2013, Quoc and Mikolov 2014). We hypothesise that operators of multiple listings will re-use terms and turns of phrase; while 'copy and paste' from one listing to another is readily detectable, some operators will fine-tune the wording for each listing and so more complex approaches will be required to find 'similar' listings.

We can then combine the outputs of these models in order to predict whether or not any individual listing is likely to be part of a ghost operation and evaluate model performance using known and visible 'multi-hosts' and hotels.

4. Initial Findings

NLP models produce high-dimensional matrices ($m \times 100\text{--}300$ is common) in which 'similarity' can be found in a number of ways: clustering (HDBSCAN) and *cosine* similarity are two that we've examined so far. For now, we are investigating how the intersection of multiple proximity types (spatial, amenity, document similarity, and word and document vector clusters) supports identification. **Table 1** provides a sense of how this performs with known hotel listings.

[†] We have not had time to explore this approach yet.

Table 1 Known Hotels & Match Rate.

Hotel Name	Match Ratio (Found vs. Known)
Arlo NoMad	1.000000
Arlo SoHo	0.968750
Arthouse Hotel	1.000000
Casamia 36	0.681641
Chamber Hotel	1.000000
Gowanus Inn	0.621302
Hosteeva	1.000000
Hotel Mela	1.285714
Incentra Village Guest House	1.074380
LYRIC 70 Pine NYC	1.000000
Manhattan At Times Square	0.542222
Nesva Hotel	1.102041
Paramount Hotel	1.020408
Park Lane	1.000000
Row NYC	0.702479
Royalton	0.625000
Royalton Park Avenue	0.604938
Shelburne Hotel & Suites By Affinia	1.000000
Stanley	1.792969
The James New York - SoHo	0.959184
The Knickerbocker	0.727811
The Michelangelo	1.000000
The Roger Hotel	1.000000
The Wagner Hotel	1.142857
The Watson Hotel	1.000000
WeWork	0.812500

The next step in this work is to explore performance on the listings *as a whole*. This is computationally demanding and calls for additional optimisation and design work, but the initial results are promising.

5. Contribution

The ability to incorporate textual analysis techniques into spatial analytic pipelines is, for us, one of the most exciting recent developments in computing: here, by allowing us to incorporate new types and measures of ‘proximity’, NLP may allow us to uncover hidden relationships between entities. While the immediate residential pressures from the growth and professionalization of the Airbnb platform may have receded during the pandemic (a rough estimate is a decline of 10–15%), we expect that they will—eventually—return, and that cities will need tools with which to understand the challenges that neighbourhoods face.

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6. Acknowledgements

The authors wish to acknowledge the invaluable contribution of InsideAirbnb by making data on listings available for use by researchers and advocates without restriction. In support of their mission we hope to ‘add code to the debate’ by making our work publicly-accessible in return.

7. Biographies

Wanyi recently completed her MSc at UCL’s Centre for Advanced Spatial Analysis. This paper builds

on proof-of-concept work undertaken for her dissertation—her systematic and thoughtful exploration of the data provided the essential evidence that further investigation was warranted. She is now pursuing job opportunities in spatial data science.

Jon is Associate Professor of Spatial Data Science at UCL and supervised Wanyi's MSc dissertation. The project is an outcome of his growing interest in textual data as a resource in spatial analysis pipelines and, as such, combines his experience in the study and teaching of literature, planning, and programming.